

THE IMPORTANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: Quality of education has a great deal of significance in higher education and in the modern higher education system. Nowadays, great attention is paid to the quality that ensures the competitiveness of the educational institution in the market of educational services by training qualified specialists who meet the requirements of international standards. These scientific and methodological materials cover a wide range of issues related to the use of innovative technologies to ensure the quality of world education and are designed to help create and implement a quality management system at the university, as well as other higher and secondary educational institutions.

Keywords: Quality of Education, trend, accreditation, monitoring, attestation.

Particular attention is paid to the issues of radical reform of the higher education system in our country, the introduction of innovative methods of work in the field, the popularization of advanced foreign experiences, the improvement of the quality of Education. During the study on the quality of Education, a critical analysis of the existing problems, qualifications of educators, issues related to the educational process is carried out. In this regard, the mistakes and shortcomings of higher education institutions are indicated and recommendations are made on the tasks that need to be carried out.

On the basis of the proposal, opinions and considerations expressed during the study, the Center for Higher Education Development Research and application of Advanced Technologies conducted a seminar-training on the topic "Improving the effectiveness of the quality of education in higher education and personal management" with the participation of the dean of faculties, head of departments and heads of departments of higher education institutions in the region. The work carried out in the system of Higher Education on this day, innovations will help to form and strengthen the professional qualifications and potential of the teacher.

The quality of education is the quality of life of society, the condition for its prosperity. Those who disagree with the idea that improving the quality of education should be better than now should not be found. Modern life requires a wider and

deeper knowledge and, therefore, a better education. Economic changes in the country are forcing state universities, along with traditional activities, to engage in marketing research, to improve financial management, to carry out strategic planning of their development, to expand the scope of additional professional education. The quality of education as a narrow concept is the result of a direct educational process, depending on the level of pedagogical personnel qualification, the organization of the educational and methodological process, the state of the material and technical base, intellectual potential.

In addition to the quality of education, the demand for graduates of the educational institution, their success, the success of employers of graduates includes assessment of Professional Skills, University and production relations, absence or presence of criticism. Analysis of the modern legal framework of Education shows that the need to ensure the quality of education is not a temporary reform of the Ministry of education and science, but a long-term public policy. Understanding the content of the concept and the conditions for ensuring quality education has undergone a long evolution. The meaning of the concept of “quality of education” in official documents has changed and expanded. Accordingly, following these trends in the regulatory framework in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the requirements for higher education institutions have also changed. If we refer to the words of our president, which are regularly heard in their appeals about the idea of the quality of education, the issues of its control and provision, we can clearly see the main stages of this process. The concept of accreditation in the field of education is inextricably linked with the concept of quality: accreditation is the formal recognition by the competent authorities of training in a particular educational program, in a particular university, etc., meets the established quality standards. [1]

Accreditation is the central means of ensuring important reform processes in European Higher Education Systems. Like assessment, accreditation serves to measure quality and monitor existing ones while implementing new degree programs. Accreditation, that is, the minimum standards of the content and specialization of the certification of the diploma program, professional compatibility of the given degree, consistency and harmony of the general concept of the scientific degree program are carried out after verification. The educational program is accredited for a certain period, taking into account the transparency of the assessment procedures. The process of professional expertise by professionals is managed by agencies, which also regularly review it through external evaluation. In

the context of the growth in the volume of educational services provided by the network of educational providers, the problem of the quality of education they provide remains extremely relevant. [2,3]

Accreditation is not a relatively new phenomenon in European educational culture. The state accreditation of the higher education institution has been in force since 1992. This is a mechanism by which the state guarantees the quality of education for all citizens and carries out the determination of state status. The procedure for recognizing the state consists of three stages:

- licensing-assessment of the compliance of the conditions of educational activities with the requirements of the state for the level of classrooms, laboratory equipment, the composition of professors and teachers, educational literature;
- certification - assessment of the content, level and quality of training of graduates in compliance with the requirements of the state educational standard;
- accreditation-determination of the status of state accreditation by Types (institution of higher education) and types (Institute, Academy, University) of the University with the designation of the list of educational programs of higher professional education (confirmation for the next term). It has the right to issue documents on education of the state sample of the University. One of the main factors in the success of any organization is the quality of the results of its activities. One of the effective methods of ensuring the quality of education is the use of international quality management standards, which, along with accreditation, regulate various aspects of the organization's activities. A similar approach is used in many foreign universities. Achieving the required level of quality that meets the requirements of all interested parties is the result of the performance of a quality management system created, introduced and certified by a third party.

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